

SOME LITTLE-KNOWN PHENOMENA IN NATURE. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK.

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Abstract

Fundamental, applied and technological research in the field of torsion (taxion etc.) fields is at a beginning of a journey. Like any new direction in science and technology, it is vulnerable to criticism, since the number of emerging questions is much greater than the answers to them.

Harmony is what keeps the world grounded. The universe was not created by the big bang, but rather by the harmonic oscillations of matter, the "original melody" that creates the universe over and over again. This idea is not only scientifically interesting, but also a social relevant.

Keywords: Physical Vacuum, Virtual Particles, Torsion Field Generators, Torsion Signal Receiver

The article describes the phenomena that cannot be described from the point of view of orthodox physics. It is assumed that the "fundamental" physical theory to be developed should be able to include the intelligent consciousness of elementary particles. This theory will allow us to reach a deeper level of description of physical phenomena. Prominent British physicist, Nobel Prize laureate Roger Penrose points out that this new, as yet absent theory, must be "uncomputable", that is, so that its action cannot be modeled by a Turing machine. The practical results described in the article may advance theoretical ideas for the creation of a new physical "fundamental" theory.

The modern doctrine of torsion fields (lepton, tachyon, longitudinal waves, neutrinos, etc.) has a completely phenomenological character, manifested in the complete absence of an explanation of the very nature of the subject of research and is limited only to a description of phenomena and processes. Developers use the assumption that virtual particles are carriers of torsion fields, allowing them to develop and implement into everyday practical activities a whole range of devices and systems designed to solve the problems of protecting the population from the negative effects of torsion fields of a certain type, new types of communication.

This modern doctrine will be based on internal simplicity and on the interaction of elementary particles with atomic nucleons.

It is known that atomic nucleons - protons and neutrons - are held together by a strong interaction. But the theory of the strong force was not developed to explain how nucleons stick together.

For years, physicists didn't understand how to use the strong force to understand the stickiness of protons and neutrons. One problem was the bizarre nature of the strong force—it gets stronger with distance, rather than slowly fading away. This feature prevented them from using their usual computational techniques.

It is believed that physical objects that are saturated with energies and represent ordinary matter are a particular form of matter infinitely refined and infinitely fast in its vibrations. It is able to penetrate any ordinary matter and create a source of movement everywhere. It is located between the atoms of a crystal

and the molecules of a living organism, and when it produces a local effect or when it is free, it is the same cosmic phenomenon or matter in motion, which we perceive as material energy and hardly imagine it as a specific form of matter in motion.

Oliphant, commenting on this view of energy, says: "It is nothing more and nothing less than what we habitually call 'spirit'. The mind is built into this unusual matter, as well as the will and any emotions. Jacob Boehme called it "celestial substance", and Swedenborg - "natural and spiritual atmospheres, composed of discrete particles of the smallest form." Prof. Crookes invented the word "protyle". Prof. Konas calls it "soul stuff" or biogen, while the Initiates call it "astral fluid» [1].

Over time, there is a certain definite change in terminology (torsion waves, tachyon waves, gravitational waves, vacuum compression waves, proton resonance). However, this does not at all mean a change in theory, but rather a constant attempt to represent a hitherto largely unknown natural phenomenon in an optimal way.

The most fundamental building block of our universe are atomic elements - virtual electrons and positrons, as we know them, which have their own consciousness [2].

Evidence of the consciousness of virtual electrons and positrons is the fact of harmonization of the Physical Vacuum in a closed volume at the connection of the left and right nodes of the geopathogenic zones of the Earth. Harmonization of the Physical Vacuum also occurs when the poles of a permanent magnet are connected. In addition, when two cacti of different geometries are connected with a simple thread or when a man and a woman hold hands, harmony ensues. The same applies to the Mobius strip. Under the state of harmony in the above-mentioned cases, we consider the state of the Physical Vacuum, when there is no negative influence of virtual electrons on the living. It is known that around most objects, including metallic ones, with the exception of some, for example, magnesium, there is a left field of virtual electrons during the day. If magnesium, which has a right-hand torsion field during the day, is brought to a metal wire around which there are virtual electrons, the virtual positrons of magnesium will repel the virtual electrons of the wire and there will

be a right-hand torsion field around the wire. This fact can be confirmed by the biolocation method or by using the VEGA-12 Ukrainian-made device [3].

During the day, as mentioned above, there is a left-handed torsion field around a metal wire, and if you put a steel plate on the wire, which also has a left-handed field, the torsion field of virtual electrons around the conductor disappears.

The magnet can also be used to demonstrate the interaction of torsion (tachyon) fields, given that the north magnetic pole has a left-handed torsional field during the day and a right-handed torsional field at night. This demonstrates the interaction of solar radiation with the environment during the day, and the reflected radiation of the moon at night. In fact, this is quantum consciousness.

But what is quantum consciousness? For example, Erwin Laszlo addressed this issue in his numerous publications, but this issue deserves a deeper consideration, including when probing elementary particles [4].

Common sense suggests that human consciousness is a stream of experience created by the brain. As long as the brain functions, there is consciousness; when the brain turns off, consciousness disappears. However, this is not necessarily the case. The brain picks up the signals, transforms them and reflects the result in the stream of our conscious experience. This is the essence of the standard scientific explanation of our perception of the world, but it is incomplete. It is incomplete not only because it cannot solve the age-old mystery of philosophers, how physical signals can be transformed into deeply felt conscious experience, and whether this transformation is the work of the brain, or whether the brain also transmits forms of consciousness from the surrounding world through virtual particles that also have consciousness, although far removed from the consciousness of people.

The development of quantum consciousness of elementary particles can be the biggest step that will allow us to overcome the problems that threaten our life and future.

Scientists have not yet finally decided on the definition of virtual particles, and this concept has not received wide support among orthodox scientists. It is believed that it is an integral part of longitudinal waves, torsion fields, tachyon fields, etc. Most likely, these are the same particles isotropically filling space.

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It is interesting to consider some synchronization phenomena in nature. Synchronization (from the Greek *συνχρόνος* - simultaneous) is a dynamic mode characterized by the periodic simultaneous activation of vibrations of a certain number of objects, molecules, electrons, a population of neurons, etc. Due to the fact that the term "synchronization" is quite common and is often used in various fields of science , its exact

definition can vary greatly depending on the specific field of application. It turned out that there are materials in which spin polarization oscillations occur spontaneously and are constantly maintained.

When many people applaud on some occasion, quiet spontaneously without any instruction, after a while the applause becomes synchronous. The phenomenon of synchronization is manifested at all levels of nature, from the synchronization of human applause to the synchronization of the movement of virtual electrons in coils wound by wire or optical fiber.

There is a phenomenon in which, during a chemical reaction, the colors of the liquid in which this reaction takes place change. That is, these substances behave like pendulums and this phenomenon occurs when a large number of molecules interact. These waves arise due to changes in the concentrations of the components of the reaction and are chemical waves, not water waves.

The water in the bottle remains water until a certain critical temperature, gradually cooling, and then abruptly begins to change its state, i.e. abruptly begins to transition from the liquid phase to the solid phase. That is, it is a temporary, and not, as it were, a version of the same story that is related to some level of connection between molecules. That is, water particles fix their phases in time to a certain level of connection between molecules, and at this time crystallization in time is what we call synchronization.

Synchronization occurs between two or more metal rings, which are suspended on threads. A separate ring generates two cones of torsion fields - left and right, and at some distance the field level goes to zero, and between the tops of the cones, the Coulomb plane is located perpendicular to them. The optimal distance between the rings for the synchronization mode is equal to their diameter.

A concave mirror has a left-handed torsion field, and if a magnet is placed at the focus of a mirror that has, for example, only a left-handed field, then the reflected left-hand field will become right-handed, and is significantly enhanced due to the focusing property of the concave mirror. If you place another concave mirror in the room with a single-pole magnet at the focus, then all three systems will be synchronized after some time, i.e. mirrors with magnets in focus are synchronized by a system of two suspended rings. And these synchronous vibrations spread throughout the apartment. Interesting fact: neither magnesium, which is right-field during the day, nor iron, which is left-field during the day, generate the corresponding fields. It is also impossible to detect left torsion fields, i.e. virtual electrons, which under normal conditions are present in the form of a fur coat around the conductor. When placed opposite one of the mirrors of any mirror, generation stops. These phenomena require additional research.

Synchronization also occurs between mirrors located vertically. During the day, the mirror surface has a left field, which is a consequence of the reflection of the sun's rays. But when you check the polarity of the radiation of the mirror in the bathroom without light

during the day, the field will be right. When the light is on, the field becomes left.

However, it turned out that materials exist in which oscillations of spin polarization occur spontaneously and are continuously maintained.

Fig.1

of high purity (99.999 %) generates alternation torsion field (TF) with a period of about 40 seconds, and the period of an alternating TF depends on the time of the day. It means that it is a system demonstrating spatial-temporal self-organization – the transfer from the state of generating the left TF to the state of generating the right TF. It is important to note that torsion fields on the opposite planes of the disk placed horizontally, are opposite, i.e., if there is the right field on one plane of the disk, there will be the left field on the opposite side.

A ring suspended during the day generates left and right torsion fields in different directions from the ring itself. But when two metal rings are suspended during the day at a short distance from each other, harmonic oscillations occur in them.

Neutrino Energy.

In recent years, intensive studies of the properties of graphene-based nano material have been carried out. The team of this company managed to develop a generator made of multilayer nano material based on graphene, so far the only known material capable, in their opinion, of converting the kinetic energy of waves of matter (invisible spectrum radiation) and thermal oscillations of its atoms into electric current due to the mechanism of "graphene wave" formation. Despite the fact that the radiation energy of the invisible spectrum is many times inferior to the radiation energy of the visible spectrum, the scientific and technological company Neutrino Energy Group has managed to create a material and device that not only converts the energy of the surrounding waves of matter, but also increases it many times, and at the same time does not violate the law of energy conservation [5.6]. Harmonic oscillations of "graphene waves", which are, in our opinion, the synchronous orbital motion of the electrons of the graphene two-dimensional plate, turning into a resonance similar to the synchronous movement of metronomes, are in fact, the work performed at the microlevel, at the micro particle level, necessary to convert the synchronous orbital motion of electrons of graphene atoms into electric current. "Graphene waves" lead to the emergence of an electro moving force (EMF) in each layer of graphene due to the interaction of magnetic and electric fields.

Experiments have established that an aluminium disk (Fig.1)

There is an assumption that at synchronous rotation of electrons along the orbitals around the nuclei of the graphene atom in the physical vacuum a certain ether wind is created, which is a consequence of the rotation of electrons. Under the influence of ether wind the crystal lattice of graphene starts to be excited and enters into resonance with this ether wind, due to which some amount of electron flow is released.

The base of the nano material, created by scientists from Neutrino Energy Group, has 12 to 20 layers of graphene alternating with layers of silicon and layers of alloying elements. Given that neutrinos and other particles of matter fields have super penetrating abilities, the multilayer nature of graphene in the nano material, as well as its placement in densely packed stacks of plates placed in an insulated enclosure, allows the same particles to excite atoms of graphene layers to the entire depth of the compressed plates.

Although this first approach deals with relatively small values of virtual particle currents, it gives us strong grounds to support further research on virtual particles and the torsion field in the living world as an electromagnetically independent phenomenon. However, given the scientific challenge that virtual particles represent, it is natural that at the current stage of research there are more questions to be answered and more experiments to be conducted than clear answers. Nevertheless, it is fair to say that a milestone has been established in the study of the principle of interaction of real and virtual particles.

It can be said that this discovery and research of the properties of graphene, as well as its applied use in the near future, will completely change our worldview in the field of potential frontiers of science development and new opportunities for technologists, engineers and inventors. But for this it is necessary to take into account that all elementary particles have their own consciousness, which controls their behavior. Naturally, this consciousness is different from human consciousness, but additional research is needed to establish this fact.

However, problems also arise when using the mentioned technology. Graphene power generation systems emit left torsion fields (tachyons, neutrinos), as do cell phones, cell phone base stations, Wi-Fi, high-voltage power lines, and other sources of

electromagnetic radiation. The company Spinor International has developed a number of devices to protect living beings from the mentioned negative radiation. www.spinor.kiev.ua

Towards a new communication paradigm

As the world grapples with information overload, cybersecurity threats and data latency, neutrinovoltaic communication represents a new solution that could change the way we interact. The Neutrino project - a new information paradigm - is a testament to the Neutrino Energy Group's unwavering commitment to innovation and sustainable development.

Indeed, Neutrino 12742 is not just an attempt to create a new communications network; it's a bold statement that the future of communication lies in the invisible, subtle power of neutrinos. And in this endeavor, Neutrino Energy is at the forefront, creating a new paradigm for global connectivity. [6. <https://neutrino-energy.com/>].

It is necessary to recall the message in New Physics that on October 27, 2001, a world-first public demonstration of telecommunications free from electric smog [7.] Participants from all part of Germany were able to witness a unique physical experiment that was carried out by Wokfratshausen institute for Spase-Energy Research in memory of Leonard Euler: the experimental transmission of language signals between

Germany and another country. Dr.rer.nat. Hartmut Muller used naturally occurring standing gravitational waves as the transmitting medium. Gravielectric energy converter allow for a coupling with the cosmic gravitational background field, while modulation and demodulation is achieved by biologically harmonizing oscillators. Standing gravitational waves organize all particles in the universe into synchronous oscillation which explains why this particular language transmission could take place without time delay. Unfortunately, there were no more publications on this topic.

A torsion signal receiver developed in Ukraine:

As stated earlier, a bioelectronic system was used as the first torsion receiver. The operation of the receiver was based on the property of tissue cells to change the conductivity of membranes under the action of a torsion field. It turned out that the conductivity of the resistances also changes under the action of the torsion field. The left torsion field decreases the conductivity, while the right field increases the conductivity. This property of resistors was used in the Winston bridge, as a result of which we received a clear electrical response to the effects of torsion fields of different polarity (Fig.2). The torsion field receiver was developed by Spinor International [8] .

Fig.2

It has been experimentally proven that it is difficult to transfer information outside the near-field zone of a torsion transmitter. However, if the spin attribute of a certain region D of Physical Vacuum (PV) is introduced into the structure of the emitted torsion signal, then the emitted torsion signal outside the near-field zone will self-focus in its local region D *. The nonlocal nature of the interaction of individual regions D and D * of the PV corresponds to the nonlocal nature of the torsion signal transmission from one point in space to another. For torsion communication systems, the role of the spin feature at transmission and reception is played by special spin (torsion) matrices. A very important circumstance is a consequence of the above. The torsion signal is explicitly present in a small vicinity of the torsion transmitter D and in the local area D * of the torsion receiver, and between them, regardless of the distance, the torsion signal is unobservable - it seems to be absent. This determines the ideal confidentiality of information transmission. The presence of an addressable torsion matrix makes it possible to implement a multicast mode of operation of a torsion communication network. Two types of samples of torsion communication products were

developed in Ukraine: communication on longitudinal (torsion, tachyon waves) and on E-H waves.

Electromagnetic-free torsion field generators:

Let's consider two simplest generators of torsion fields. Such generators will be used in an increasing number of applications, such as in the development of torsion communication, but the key theoretical questions about how it works remain unanswered. An approach based on the physics of consciousness of virtual particles can help bridge this gap, an L-C circuit (Fig. 3), also called a resonant circuit, or tuned circuit, is an electric circuit consisting of an inductor, represented by the letter L, and a capacitor, represented by the letter C, connected together. Oscillatory processes occurring in such a circuit are well studied if the capacity C was initially charged. However, it was found that in such a chain harmonic oscillations of virtual particles spontaneously arise. This is like an analogue of graphene waves, which are created by real electrons, but in contrast to them, vibrations are carried out by virtual electrons. Fluctuations can be detected using the VEGA-12 device manufactured by Spinor International, or by dowsing.

It means that the L-C system also demonstrates spatial - temporal self-organization - the transition from the state of generation of the left TF to the state of generation of the right TF. The surprise is that harmonic oscillations are amplified in amplitude if the coil leads are short-circuited. There are some features in the work of such a coil.

Fig.3

Fig.4

From what has been considered, it inevitably follows that the radiation characteristics will depend on the shape of the material structures on which the metal wire or optical fiber is wound or placed inside and the

It is known that around a straight wire at some distance from its surface there are virtual electrons repelled by real electrons. The same phenomenon occurs in electron beam devices with a heated cathode. Virtual electrons, removed at some distance from the cathode itself due to their repulsion by real electrons, when heating is applied to the filament, become real, and do not evaporate from the cathode, as was thought until now [8].

When winding wires around a coil (Fig.4), harmonic oscillations of virtual electrons and positrons arise. For example, if virtual electrons appear at one end of the coil depending on the location of the coil relative to the north-south direction, then at the opposite end of the coil positrons are collected and the process then continues.

method of connecting the ends of their coils to their centers. Let's consider a more complex option, when we have two coils wound on one pipe, wound in opposite directions (Fig.4).

Fig.5

Fig. 5 shows one of the two pipes that have two coils wound in opposite directions. The coils are wound with wire from the same coil, on the same pipe that has been cut, so we have two pipes, each with two coils wound, which means that the coils are in a tangled state. The coils are arranged horizontally. These coils will generate alternating torsional fields of sinusoidal type. At the same time, it is possible to switch the coils to a mode where only the right fields are generated, or only the left fields. To do this, place one of the coil outputs into the middle of the same coil, resulting in a half-sine wave of positive or negative polarity. The change in the

shape of the signal produced by the coils depends on which end of the wire of one of the coils is inserted into the middle of the pipe, because there is a right-handed torsion field inside the pipe.

In general, the tube itself focuses the positrons because opposite virtual particles repel, i.e. virtual electrons that also exist on the inner wall of the tube repel the virtual positrons towards the centre, and this minus gives them additional focus. When connected to the tube from either end of the battery negative, the radiation beam becomes smaller in diameter, i.e. it is focused. When connected to the pipe from either end of

the battery's positive terminal, the generation disappears.

To put it simply, the task was to test the simultaneous operation of several torsion field generators that had different numbers of turns, i.e. they generated different frequencies. It turned out that the generators are phase synchronized, i.e. the spins of elementary particles of all generators are transferred to an entangled state and the dominant frequency is the lowest frequency of one of the generators. Statistical observations have shown that in this case the spins of elementary particles are free, but correlate with each other. Similar experiments are carried out almost continuously, more and more accurately and perfectly - and the result is the same. For example, if during the daytime several such generators operate synchronously and the LC generator is put vertically, that is, so that generation stops, and then other generators stop generating torsion fields. These and other phenomena require careful study to understand the nature of the interaction of torsion fields in nature. This happens, in our opinion, because elementary particles have consciousness. None of the areas of modern science associated with the recognition of the existence of virtual particles includes in its consideration their consciousness, which, naturally, differs from the consciousness of people. Particles behavior is purposeful, particles exchange information during interaction. They have correlated idea of space and time and is easy to enter the synchronous generating mode. Our results motivate the widespread use of torsion field generation methods in future research and development of torsion communication.

Phenomena in the magnet.

During the research, new phenomena were discovered. It turned out that if a permanent magnet stays in an alternating torsion field for a long time - in the field of a torsion pendulum - than its torsion fields disappear, although the magnet itself attracts iron objects. However, if a normal magnet with its corresponding torsion fields is placed in a torsion screen (it can be a material with a pronounced orthogonal structure or ordinary foam rubber) and then this magnet is placed on another magnet that has no torsion fields, then this magnet will develop torsion fields. If we take into account that the aforementioned orthogonal structures are a screen for torsion fields and freely transmit magnetic fields, then the thought arises that magnetic fields passing through a torsion screen have some information component that induces torsion fields in a magnet in which these fields were absent. This phenomenon could be called magnetic - torsion induction. But if you separate the magnet in the screen from another magnet, then the torsion fields in the latter disappear. Subsequent experiments made it possible to establish that it is possible to restore the torsion field of a magnet that has lost it as a result of the action of alternating torsion fields. This method is similar to the method of recording right-hand torsion fields on the Spinor device. It should be emphasized that we are at the beginning of a long period of research into the features of torsion fields. It seems we are in search of an understanding of the laws of torsion interactions.

Undoubtedly, the unity of the world is informational in nature. The formulated concepts should be considered only as a formulation of a problem that requires in-depth study, especially if we take into account the well-known limitations of models for describing torsion interactions. The consciousness of elementary particles plays a decisive role in physical processes. This tradition, which has a long tradition, allows us to naturally explain the apparent non locality and other paradoxes of the quantum world. We should mention that the Ukraine physicists noticed more than a decade ago that spin perturbations in spin medium are propagating in such a way that they cannot be screened, which in those times had no relation to the torsion fields. It means that there is a possibility of underwater and underground telecommunications, as well as communications through any other natural medium.

7. Possible Mechanisms of the TF Influence on a Human

Unfortunately, the scientific data accumulated by the present time is not enough to explain the majority of the objectively existing biological phenomena connected with influence of TF on a human, therefore it is only possible to make a number of assumptions on the phenomenological level.

It was earlier believed that the control on all levels of organization of a bio object is conducted by weak EMFs and torsion field activating or deactivating various processes.

Torsion field of TV sets, mobile phones, base stations of mobile phones, geo pathogenic zones of the Earth, as well as diverse symbols indented on a metal or a dielectric material, as well as permanent magnets may be the emitters of such sort, forming weak but determined torsion control signals on the level of organs, tissues and cells. The mentioned weak determined signals are a modifying factor of a low intensity with a wide range of biological action. Among the many hypotheses and conjectures about the mechanism of the adverse effect of torsion fields on living organisms is the hypothesis of free radicals.

A free radical is an electrically charged particle, as a free radical lacks an electron. In order to become a stable particle, free radicals must "steal" this lacking electron from another molecule. When the electron has been stolen, for example, from a bacterium, its molecular structure has been damaged, which leads to its death. When there are no bacteria left to be destroyed and when there is not enough electrons which can be obtained from antioxidants to stabilize the number of excessive free radicals, the free radicals then proceed to the single sources they can steal electrons from - to healthy cells. As a result, healthy cells are damaged and perish from the loss of electrons stolen by free radicals; then an additional signal is sent to the immune system to receive further help. This creates a continuous autoimmune reaction (creation of more free radicals) which leads to chronic inflammation and tissue damage which is usually called oxidative stress.

Chronic overproduction of free radicals by the immune system causes such inflammatory diseases as arthritis, atherosclerosis, infarction, type 2 diabetes,

lupus, multiple sclerosis, asthma, inflammatory bowel diseases etc.

Magnets

The first person to find, back in 1936, the difference between the effect of the north and the south pole of a strong magnet on a live matter and water, was doctor Davis. He believed that if the “spin” is directed against the impulse, the helicity is called left (l), if down the impulse – right (r), i.e., in his opinion, there are two symmetric emissions, one of which contains “left” particles and the other contains “right” ones. Later he studied this fact in detail and came to the conclusion that the lines of flux coming out of S are twisted clockwise, and the lines entering N are twisted counter-clockwise. Doctor Davis determined the helicity of the emission viewing it as if along the magnetic lines of flux for each pole. For practical purposes it is more comfortable to determine the helicity is in the direction opposite to the way it was made by Davis. The modern idea has it that the north pole during the day has the right field and it accelerates all the processes of evolution and growth, and the south pole slows them down.

Conclusion

Human settlements have an impact on the physical environment; they change locally the properties of the soil and, through it, have effects on humans and animals.

The relay antennas, the wind turbines and possibly other an electrical installations (transformers, pylons, motors, etc.) may present a danger to the health of

Living beings several kilometers away if they are at the intersection of the fault zones used for the circulation of water. The fault is the way of transmission of these «geo technopathogenic” nuisances.

Sustainable exposure to these nuisances can cause the dysfunctions of the body and the behavioral problems or diseases in humans and animals.

The geomorphological study from the geological and topographical maps makes it possible to identify if electrical installations and the place where the nuisances occur are located on the same fault zone.

The installation of protections Vernada device or plug - in Vernada - Geo device in network of the base station supply generally makes it possible to correct nuisances.

Conclusions

A genuine safety torsion field (taxion field) standard needs to be established to serve as a basis for future regulatory decisions. Since the specific absorption rate alone does not measure biological effects on humans, it does not serve the safety needs of consumers.

Recommendations: Science, medicine and governments must move immediately and aggressively with the goal of minimizing the impact of torsion fields on children, pregnant women and adults.

One agency must be designated as the lead agency for protecting people who use wireless communication devices .

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